

Living Labs – an Approach for achieving Sustainable Change in City Logistics

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Abstract

The Living lab is an approach that allows for improving the co-creation processes, putting the end-users at the heart of innovation, realizing new business models, looking for new roles for traditional stakeholders in the innovation process, and a more directed innovation preparation and deployment process. This article describes experiences of eight European cities in setting up and developing living labs in city logistics within the CIVITAS 2020 CITYLAB project and draws upon the CITYLAB Deliverable 3.4 “Practical guidelines for establishing and running living laboratories”. It provides a distinction between logistics service living labs and city logistics transition living lab. The article shares experiences on setting up and operation of the living labs and added value from using living labs set up.

Keywords: *city logistics, living labs, co-creation, sustainable transition.*

1 Introduction

Environmental, societal and economic sustainability is in the heart of the transition process that our society is undergoing today. UN and EU sustainability goals and objectives address all emission intensive sectors, setting up clear targets that have to be achieved in order to change current trends. Setting up transition pathways is than responsibility of these concrete sectors, choosing the most appropriate and effective strategies and methods.

In this framework there is an increasing interest in city logistics innovations, due to the associated negative impacts on air quality, noise, livability, climate change and use of urban space. Solutions to address these challenges are complex in terms of different stakeholders and different interests involved. In spite of the many trialed solutions to address these challenges, no large-scale steps towards more sustainable city logistics processes are yet set. Even if experiments are proved financially and technically successful, scaling up, transferring and bringing significant impact is lacking.

The living lab approach is a new for city logistics sector. It allows for improving the co-creation processes, putting the end-users at the heart of innovation, realizing new business models, looking for new roles for traditional stakeholders in the innovation process, and a more directed innovation preparation and deployment process. In this way, the speed of the transition process in urban freight increases as well as the rate of successful city logistics innovation uptake. This paper presents the results of the CIVITAS 2020 CITYLAB project (2015 – 2018) and draws upon CITYLAB's Deliverable 3.4 "Practical guidelines for establishing and running living laboratories" (CITYLAB, 2018a). CITYLAB was established with the objective to develop solutions that result in roll-out, up-scaling and further implementation of cost effective strategies, measures and tools for emission free city logistics in urban centres by 2030. The project looked into the development of the city logistics solutions within living laboratories in eight European cities: Amsterdam, Brussels, London, Oslo, Paris, Rome, Rotterdam, Southampton. Research zooms in and builds up conclusions on the experience with two types of living labs: urban transition living labs and service/product-oriented living labs.

2 Living labs in city logistics

According to Maas et al (2017), nowadays a living lab can be referred to as "a concept for achieving a long-term sustainable solution for a societal challenge by involving the actual end-user. It can also be a method to achieve a certain objective by connecting

and involving the right stakeholders and follow an iterative design and learning cycle called co-creation. Finally, a living lab can also refer to the context, related to the organizational or geographical environment for the real-world experiments". Although the term 'Living Lab' is frequently used, referring to a wide variety of local experimental projects of participatory nature, a shared definition is still lacking. However, several key elements that are essential for a living lab can be determined: experiments take place in a real-world environment; co-creation and end-user involvement is essential for the process of innovation development; involvement of multidisciplinary competences and multi-stakeholder participation; an iterative learning cycle, referring to the process where innovations are developed following "plan-do-check-act" cycles.

Depending on the initial objective of the Living Lab, these principles can be either used to find a solution for a concrete problem via development, testing and upscaling of an innovative product or service or to guide a transition process on the city / neighborhood / street level. Looking into the city logistics environment, two types of living labs can be distinguished:

- *Logistics service living labs* - the living lab concept is applied on the level of the individual companies, working out logistics innovations;
- *City logistics transition living labs* - the living lab concept is applied on the city-wide framework, helping out cities in making a transition to, for example, zero emission city logistics.

If logistics service living lab follows the concepts and practices related to product or service innovation research, city logistics transition living labs are closely connected to the urban transition theories and their main characteristics are well illustrated by Nevens et al (2013), Roorda et al (2014), Wittmayer et al (2014).

Table summarizes the main differences between these two types of living labs.

Table 1. Logistics service living labs and city logistics transition living labs

Logistics service living lab	City logistics transition living lab
Short-term perspective targeted at specific solutions	Long-term perspectives targeted at big societal problem
Detailed oriented and narrower thematically. Often linked to a company's objective or business goals.	Shared ambitions and goals of the living lab and linked to the city and / or country's objectives or goals.
Medium-term collaboration with a strong focus on the participation of the end-user in the co-creation process	Long-term collaboration of quadruple helix stakeholders and roadmap development and co-creation of actions

Iterative cycles are focused on the development of the solution for one specific issue at hand.	Several different solutions are trialled in parallel, including different stakeholders, but all contributing to the final living lab ambition
Clearly defined end-users: innovation developed in this lab should meet their needs	End-users depend on the concrete solution trialled
Usually driven by industry	Usually driven by public authorities and knowledge institutes

Source: CITYLAB, 2018b

Logistics service living labs are privately driven collaborations that aim to address concrete operational problems or challenges that private stakeholders are facing. These are, for example: improving efficiency of shipping process, addressing new category of customers, developing and rolling-out new services. They are usually initiated by private city logistics stakeholders with the main emphasis on improving the services they directly control. The attention is on the process of the solution co-creation with an end-user(s). Those are usually clearly defined from the beginning, as developed innovation in the living lab should meet their needs. Logistics service living labs have shorter ambition focus and are finalized once innovation roll out took place.

City logistics transition living labs are usually initiated by public actors or local interest groups with the objective to guide transition process in the specific geographical area (city, neighborhoods, street). A living lab is then an action-driven partnership where local governmental stakeholders cooperate with industry, retail, commerce, academic and societal partners and collaboratively develop new approaches and actions to promote sustainable logistics. Shared ambitions and goals of the living lab are often thematically and linked to the city and / or country's objectives or goals, addressing, for example such problems as: reducing emissions and noise; improving accessibility and livability of the area; reducing congestion; improving safety.

Logistics innovations are developed within an ecosystem on the city level which can facilitate innovation development process or act as a barrier for it. Political and policy support for the urban freight, existence of efficient stakeholder communication and cooperation platforms, monitoring and evaluation of urban freight solutions and the existence of efficient knowledge transfer channels are defined as the key components of the logistics living lab ecosystem (Nesterova et al., 2018). Existence of favorable city logistics ecosystem provides local authorities, industry partners and knowledge institutes with an opportunity to work more efficiently together on the local logistics problems. This ecosystem facilitates the knowledge transfer within the living labs, therefore new solutions can build up on the learnings from the previous trials.

Experiences in setting up and operating living labs in city logistics

During the three years of the CITYLAB project, valuable experiences were obtained on setting up, operating, or trying to start living labs in city logistics. CITYLAB investigated and contributed to the application of the living lab principles within both types of living labs in city logistics:

- In Rotterdam, Paris and Southampton the project assisted city-wide transition processes contributing to zero emission city logistics;
- In Amsterdam, Rome, Oslo, London and Brussels concrete solutions and services were trialed and upscaled using living lab principles.

This section presents some of the experiences in working with and developing of living labs in city logistics.

Setting up a city logistics living lab

For both types, the first step in setting up a living lab is **to define clear ambition and objectives**, agreeing on the main reason of the creation of the living lab and on what should be achieved as a living lab result. The creation of logistics service living labs is usually initiated by a private party trying to address a specific problem. As a result, the living lab ambition focuses on finding a solution for this problem. These ambitions are usually short term and the time necessary to develop the innovative solution is relatively limited. The city logistics transition living labs mostly emerge from the existing and obstinate problems in the street, neighborhood or city. Several actors together try to address the issues and to find common solutions. Often, the ambition of a transition living labs is related to a long-term city development vision and is supported by all living lab participants. Experiences from CITYLAB have shown that:

- The setting up phase of the living lab is very important: here you discover things you might not have expected, as partnerships are relatively new and, in this phase, you learn other participants' values, interests and ideas related to the jointly developed ambition and goals;
- During operation of the living lab it is necessary to regularly check whether the ambitions and the scope of the Living Lab and the individual participants' ambitions and interests are still aligned. Critical changes in the living lab itself and its ecosystem that can influence the implementation process should be monitored. For example, partners that were part of the common definition of the living lab's ambition and objectives can change jobs. As a result, the group has to get used to a new person, and a new person has to gain confidence in the process and the group;

- Take personal animosities between key figures of organisations into account. Identify the risk of non-compliance from either of the organisations and take mitigating actions when possible.

Once the ambition is agreed, the scope of the Living Lab within the real-world environment have to be made clear. “Inviting the respective parties to engage in the living lab’s real-world experiment is a promising option because public authorities, companies, and others can be more willing to overcome established attitudes and obstacles as long as it is ‘only’ in an experimental setting (...). The experimental setting also encourages a critical attitude and the search for creative solutions” (Steen & van Bueren, 2017). For the city logistics system, this implies the urban area, where the geographical scope and location of the real-life experiments will depend on the key goals of the (city logistics transition living) lab.

Logistics service living labs focus on solving a specific stakeholder’s problem and on the users of the developed innovation. So the area is determined by the end-users of innovative solution and can vary from a single building, street, neighbourhood(s) or group of customers. It can be limited by the policy regulated zone (e.g. low emission zone; congestion charge zone) or any other area or set of areas where this particular innovative solution can be trailed out and has potential to be upscaled. For example, within CITYLAB:

- Gnewt cargo and TNT were looking for a solution to increase their urban freight transport with electric freight vehicles in inner **London**. The geographical area was limited by the congestion charge area, providing financial benefits for electric vehicles. This area became the natural geographical scope of the CITYLAB living lab implementation.
- In **Oslo** the CITYLAB living lab implementation looked how to optimise the internal logistics for shopping centres and how to reduce the vehicle waiting time, thus decreasing surrounding congestion. Therefore, the real-life test environment of the living lab implementation has been limited to a shopping mall building and the neighbouring area.

For the city logistics transition living labs the city as a whole, or some particular neighbourhood(s) or street(s) can serve as an urban test environment. The city becomes an arena to trial out multiple experiments / innovations aiming at achieving one overarching goal.

Creation of the core living lab team is a next step in setting up a living lab – this is a group of people/organizations that are interested to collaborate on the development of the living lab. To create this team, the living lab initiator has to contact potential partners, keeping in mind: idea of quadruple helix (1); end-user involvement (2); and

“out of the box” thinking as regards additional competences necessary (3). For the city logistics living labs considering the (1) category of stakeholders is specifically important, while (2) and (3) should be decided case by case for the individual implementations that might run in parallel and require different stakeholders.

City logistics issues are complex to solve as there is usually no single problem-owner and stakeholders have various objectives and stakes. Therefore, the co-creation process in living labs is important, as: it helps to align conflicting objectives and identify the common ambition in the process; and it aims to increase participation of the end-users in the development of the final product, and as a result increasing the chances of its uptake. Within logistics service living labs co-creation means actively engaging the end-users in the development of a new solution. This is a challenging process: as noted by Steen & van Bueren (2017), end-users “typically do not have a professional motive to participate in innovation processes and participate on a voluntary basis”. In London CITYLAB implementation benefited from the active involvement of industrial and research partners as well as municipality. University of Westminster, a research partner in the living lab process, performed *ex ante* and *ex post* evaluations, based on which decisions about new cycles in the solution development were taken. Involvement of the municipality in the living lab process made it possible to efficiently find necessary space for the location of the Gnewt cargo hub(s) within congestion charge area. This is a strategically important question for London, where there is a high space scarcity. This cooperation between government, industry and researchers has proven highly successful in London.

In city logistics transition living labs the combination of the quadruple helix stakeholders is a pre-requisite to guide transition. The representatives from these stakeholder groups can form “frontrunner” groups, bringing together “visionary people from various disciplines who are willing and able to engage in a creative process towards a long-term conceived future for a sustainable city” (Nevens et al., 2013). The frontrunners develop transition ambition and objectives and the roadmap towards it in time. Together they set up sustainable, user-friendly, financially feasible and, in the end scalable and / or transferable city logistics solutions. In Southampton, the Southampton City council, Meachers Global Logistics, Southampton General Hospital and the two universities (Southampton Solent University and University of Southampton) came together with a common ambition to improve local air quality by promoting best practices in sustainable logistics and reducing their respective transport footprints. A Memorandum of understanding was signed stating partners’ commitment for this cooperation process. The University of Southampton acts as the neutral co-ordinator of activities. Existing business and personal relationships between the parties, emanating from the original memorandum of understanding have been key to continue the living lab and develop and explore new ideas: e.g. consolidation initiatives, joint procurement and electric fleet adoption. Other

experiences from the CITYLAB projects have indicated that:

- Involve external stakeholders, users, customers as much as possible from the very beginning in the living lab process. Living labs should create value for all stakeholders, which makes it is easier to have stakeholders' commitment throughout the whole process.
- Convincing stakeholders to actively join a living lab from the beginning – where a lot of things still have to be defined and developed - requires some persuasiveness and vision.
- Co-creation with end-user is in the heart of the living lab approach. Participating in the development of the living lab solution, the end-user becomes more responsive in adopting these ideas;
- It is crucial for a city logistics living lab to be successful that all partners see a potential benefit from participating.

Understanding the drivers, interests, culture and way of working of all parties related to the Living Lab is important and might help with their continuous involvement in and their commitment to the living lab for a longer period. Once the core team is created, it is necessary to analyse what kind of external parties that could help living lab to achieve its goals are missing.

Selecting an appropriate governance model is a next step in setting up a living lab in city logistics. There is variety of possible governance models for living labs, the key is to find a way that works for the living lab in each specific case: a memorandum of understanding, informal agreement, working groups set up, a covenant, etc. The forming of freight partnerships or frontrunner groups could be a good start for a city logistics transition living lab. In CITYLAB:

- The living lab in **Southampton** is set up around an informal Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between the Southampton City Council and the University of Southampton on sustainable logistics. The main objective of this agreement is to reduce overall vehicle emissions and improving air quality standards. It is desirable to have as many stakeholders as possible sign up to the MoU.
- The living lab in **Rome** is set up around the European research project CITYLAB. Initially there were limited opportunities of collaboration between urban freight stakeholders and Rome CITYLAB living lab implementation acted as an opportunity to start the work on reinforcement of cooperation

between industry, research and city authorities on the question of urban freight.

- In **Oslo** there was no formal agreement between the stakeholders included in the living lab. The working group and participating stakeholders were defined based on business decisions. However, additional stakeholders outside of the company were included through regular meetings and workshops.
- The **Rotterdam** living lab is set up around the local covenant (a local Green Deal on Zero Emission City Logistics), which was signed by the city, research institute TNO and front running transport companies from varying logistics sectors.

After the core living lab team is in place and its commitment to work on commonly agreed ambition and goals within living lab set up is formalised, the operation of the living lab can start. Initial preparatory steps will include: analysis of city logistics ecosystem; identification of potential ideas and solutions to develop within a living lab and development of monitoring and measuring system.

Operation, evaluation and going through the cycles in living lab

Within living labs development of innovation follows a cyclical approach, where plan-do-evaluate – act phases are consequently used until the innovation is considered as ready to roll out or decision is taken to stop testing process. Each cycle, within a logistics service living lab can be continued into a new loop (when improvement of existing solution is necessary) or interrupted because the solution is considered as not interesting. During a cycle also, a new innovation idea can be born and be then developed within another implementation case. In Amsterdam the CITYLAB living lab implementation went through several cycles. The first cycles have assessed an initial idea (developed prior to CITYLAB project) where parcels were navigated in the city by a vessel (the floating depot) and from there distributed by clean vehicles to final destinations; this turned out to be difficult for several reasons (e.g. moving of premises to start from, developing the floating depot, finding landing places at the canals, finding suitable volumes, etc.). In the following cycles, PostNL considered the possibility to use a floating depot pushed by a hybrid-push boat from where zero emission (ZE) vehicles (EV trucks or bikes) would deliver parcels in the ‘de Pijp’ in Amsterdam, supplying pubs, restaurants and hotels with fresh food items. Ex ante evaluations and end-user consultations have indicated that there is no yet a paying customer that is ready to support this. The next cycle that was tested in the real life and resulted in the local and national (by Post NL) upscale of the solution is partial replacement of PostNL vans in the city centre of Amsterdam with specially designed e-freight bikes that distribute mail and parcels from micro-hubs located in the city centre. The overall objective: more sustainable organization of PostNL’s city logistics operations did not change during the cycles.

Other CITYLAB experiences have shown that:

- Minor adjustments can make a large difference. In some living labs it has been crucial to make small adjustments to the business models as the implementation has developed over time. This reflects the willingness of organisations to make operational changes to logistics practices in favour of sustainability when the outcome, although positive, will inherently impact (potentially negatively) on customer / client experience.
- Evaluation should be an on-going process, both on the process of the implementation cases as of the city logistics living lab.
- The living lab cycles for innovations should follow the natural development process and not be forced in fixed time frames. The living lab process is guiding the cycles.
- One should be able to recognize the act phase and go to next cycle.

At some extent, living lab approach requires changing usual ways of working for partners. CITYLAB have shown, that:

- Even if the collaborative mechanisms are already existing in the cities, it takes time to influence and steer towards the principles of working and innovating in a living lab;
- It is difficult for people to work in another way: the living lab approach requires a certain mentality change to more open-minded and open-end development of the solutions, whereas many professionals are used to plan projects and results in advance.

Learning from the negative experiences contributes to the positive experience and building up on this is a skill we need to develop in order to increase the innovation uptake level. Not all of the solutions, developed within CITYLAB according to the living lab principles were directly successful. The first cycles in Rome, Amsterdam, London and Brussels of the implementations did not result in the implementation roll out, but have produced a valuable knowledge and strong cooperation structures to move forward for the next living lab cycles. As the result sustainable city logistics solutions developed within the London and Amsterdam implementations have rolled out. The Rome implementation within a second living lab cycle is extending the implementation in terms of flows involved, sites and alternative recyclable / reusable waste. The transferability effect is also achieved on the city level, where City of Rome wants to use CITYLAB case as a “test-case” to show all the benefits derivable from the adoption of a living lab approach where stakeholders collaborate, create, validate

and test innovative technologies, services, products and systems. It intends to make use of the outcomes of the CITYLAB experience to identify the most prominent innovative freight solutions to be included in the upcoming Urban Logistic Plan and Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (2018), with the local knowledge partner (UoR) providing support. This mentality switch in approaching innovative solutions is key for the future of the innovations in city logistics. The city logistics projects are no longer only evaluated on the direct success from its implementation, but are seen in the broader perspective of added value from the establishment of stakeholder cooperation processes and contribution to the long-term goals of public authorities and market players.

Added value from the living labs approach in city logistics

Living labs in city logistics put urban logistics on the strategically important place, attracting attention of the policy-makers, knowledge institutes, research partners and citizens. CITYLAB illustrated that different stakeholder groups benefit differently from participating in living labs in city logistics (CITYLAB, 2017, 2018c).

For the city authorities, urban transition living lab gives an opportunity to reach a bottom-up policy coherence, including in the policy and decision-making process the needs and aspirations of local and regional stakeholders, industrial parties, transport operators and citizens. Overall, better knowledge and understanding of the urban freight in the city is created. Creation of frontrunner group with representatives from different sectors helps to gain a common perspective on the city logistics and better understand needs and requirements of transport stakeholders and logistics operators and barriers they are facing, thus, developing more efficient and targeted policies. Joint collaboration in the development of the solutions supports short and long-term policy planning and, through evaluation, provides a feedback on the effectiveness of the policy measures. Municipalities “could support living labs by selecting zones where its efforts are aimed at creating room in the public regulations allowing bottom up initiatives and innovations” (Steen & van Bueren, 2017). Policy-makers bring in decision-making power into the living lab process as well as possibilities to create conditions facilitating development of innovations. They also can influence increasing of investments in the innovations for city logistics.

For transport operators, logistics providers, retailers and other private stakeholders in city logistics processes, being part of the frontrunner group provides an opportunity to influence, at certain extent, the policy making process of municipalities. Next to it, it gives an efficient access to the most recent domain knowledge and evaluation of its own activity efficiency, providing an input for the improvement of the business

cases and potential for the innovation uptake. It also gives opportunity to better understand other market players and their interests. Overall, if certain transitions are to take place, being a part of the frontrunner group, helps companies not to be forced into the changes, but to co-create the shape of these changes together with other parties. Living labs facilitate a cooperative mentality switch in the supply chains: potentially competitive businesses are no more seen as competitors but as partners working together to achieve a common goal.

Both, city and industrial partners benefit from the added value brought by the research partners in the living lab process. Along with innovative ideas they bring in, research partners also provide a neutral opinion on the relevance, efficiency and sustainability of the tested solutions. Research partners can do a background literature and best practice research; undertake scoping and feasibility studies for the industry partners for minimal cost as part of managed student projects. They can act as secure data manager on behalf of the partners, undertaking ex ante and ex post analysis and providing longer term evaluation of any implemented measures. A research partner is also well positioned to be a neutral coordinator of the living lab in city logistics, specifically for the city logistics transition living labs. Being involved in the living lab, provides researches with cost efficient access to the first hand data and with an opportunity to validate their ideas with market players. New research ideas are generated via the stakeholder discussions and by going through the innovation cycles.

Stakeholder collaboration developed within living labs provides an opportunity to build relationships and establish joint initiatives in city logistics that otherwise would not have taken place.

3 Conclusion

City logistics is dynamically developing sector which gets increasing attention from public authorities due to its negative impacts on the livability of the cities and quality of life of the citizens. Living Lab concept offers a way to address complex multi-stakeholder topics: it changes the emphasis from the solution as an isolated object to the process of integration with its environment. Finding a solution becomes a process involving many stakeholders with different objectives and interests within a dynamic environment. It allows the creation of experimentation environments that are sufficiently connected with real world stakeholders and their business models, to allow near-simultaneous development and deployment. This requires a medium or long-term approach, adaptive and pro-active planning and steering.

City logistics is the system and process by which goods are collected, transported, and distributed within urban environments. It is a sector where solutions often ask for a multi-stakeholder approach, bringing together different, sometimes not aligned to each other interests. Due to the high dynamics in city logistics, it is unsure in advance what type of solution will best fit with problems faced. The creation of living labs in city logistics provides a new way to develop and address different trends and challenges in urban freight. It supports an action driven cooperation forms fostering innovation deployment and improving communication and cooperation between stakeholders. Development of the shared vision, aligning individual interests to common goals and active involvement of the end-users as well as other competencies in the co-creation process helps to develop innovative solutions that are more user-friendly, more financially sustainable and adapted/tested within a real-world environment.

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